
BLUE OCEAN STRATEGY AND SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE IN FAST MOVING CONSUMER GOOD INDUSTRY IN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT: *This study focused on the influence of blue ocean strategy and sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria. The main objective of this study was to ascertain the effect of blue ocean strategy dimensions such as value innovation, demand creation, growth and profitability on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria. The research question and hypothesis were formulated in line with the research objective. Methodologically, survey research design was adopted for the study. Related literature aimed at enriching the conceptual framework. The population of the study was 157 full-time employees and a sample size of 113 was drawn from the population using Taro Yamane Formula. The collected data were further analyzed using Simple Linear Regression at a 0.05 level of significance. Findings showed that the three independent variables (value innovation with $X1 = R2 = 63.9$, demand creation $X2 = 67.9$ at 0.05 level of significance and $X3 = 52.3$. It was concluded that by substituting competitive advantage for value innovation, demand creation, growth and profitability as the main objectives where businesses must generate customer demand and penetrate undiscovered markets blue ocean strategy aims to completely flip the conventional wisdom on strategic management. It was recommended that value innovation is a cornerstone of the blue ocean strategy and represents the simultaneous pursuit of differentiation and low cost, creating a leap in value for both the company and its customers.*

Keyword: Blue ocean strategy, value innovation, demand creation, growth and profitability and sustainable competitive advantage

Introduction

The strategy is a long-term plan for the person or the company as a whole. The strategy employed by the corporation is characterized as "positioning and linking the company/organization to its environment in a way that ensures that its success is repeated and makes sure of surprises. Organizations must implement plans for growth, stability, profitability, and efficiency, among other reasons, in order to succeed. The blue ocean strategy was developed as a response to the observation that successful economic units don't thrive via rivalry; instead, they thrive by forging new, uncharted territories and concentrating on value innovation through the provision of goods and services that benefit both the economic unit and the client. In order to achieve business growth, value innovation involves changing the focus from the competition to new products that offer value to the customer (Ekanem *et al.*, 2023). Management accounting, on the other hand, is an information system that assists the management of the economic unit in formulating, succeeding, and implementing its strategy as well as carrying out its functions. The information provided by the management accountant, which can apply the blue ocean strategy, can help the management unit achieve competitive advantage. Rather than fighting in congested industries, or red oceans, where competition is strong, the strategy encourages enterprises to establish new market spaces, or blue oceans, that are devoid of rivalry. The fundamental concept is to simultaneously pursue low cost and differentiation in order to create fresh demand and open up new market space.

Blue ocean strategy is the pursuit of low cost and differentiation at the same time to carve out new market space and generate demand. It all comes down to carving out and seizing uncontested market space, which renders the competition obsolete. It is predicated on the idea that industrial structure and market limits are malleable and subject to change based on the deeds and attitudes of participants in the market. In blue oceans, the rules of the game are yet to be established, therefore competition is moot. The wider, deeper potential offered in uncharted market space is compared to a blue ocean. A blue ocean may grow profitably because it is large, deep, and strong.

Statement of problem

Because of the fierce rivalry, market saturation, and price wars that define Nigeria's fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) industry, it is challenging for businesses to achieve sustainable growth using conventional competitive techniques. The red ocean, or congested market sector, in which the majority of FMCG companies compete, is characterized by narrow profit margins and little room for differentiation. For fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) companies hoping to prosper in Nigeria's fast-paced and frequently unstable economic environment, this scenario poses a serious challenge due to factors like price sensitivity, limited differentiation, market saturation, infrastructure issues, regulatory and economic instability, and currency fluctuations. Nigeria's FMCG sector faces a variety of obstacles that call for tenacity, creativity, and strategic planning. Businesses must comprehend and cater to a variety of customer wants while navigating economic volatility, fierce rivalry, infrastructure constraints, and regulatory concerns. These difficulties served as the basis for the investigation of how Nigeria's fast-moving consumer goods industry may maintain a sustainable competitive edge through the application of blue ocean strategy.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to ascertain the influence of blue ocean strategy and sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria. the specific objective includes;

- i. To examine the influence of value innovation on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria.
- ii. To ascertain the effect of demand creation on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria.
- iii. To investigate the impact of growth and profitability on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria.

Research Questions

- i. What is the influence of value innovation on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria?
- ii. To what extend does demand creation influence sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria?
- iii. How does growth and profitability influence sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria?

Statement of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of value innovation on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria,

H₀₂: Demand creation does not significantly influence sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria,

H₀₃: There is no significant influence growth and profitability on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria.

Review of Relevant Literature

2.1 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Model of blue ocean strategic and sustainable competitive advantage

Source: Researcher's Conceptualization, (2024).

Concept of blue ocean strategy

The goal of the blue ocean strategy is to open up new markets, or "blue oceans," as opposed to competing in already-saturated markets, or "red oceans," which are already established. The goal of the approach is to make the competition obsolete by entering and controlling uncontested market space. Global markets are directing corporations to produce a varied supply for customer demand growth, and the Blue Ocean approach transforms businesses operating in quickly evolving industries to fulfill their customers' wants. Due to this, the environmental industries are very competitive (Vignesh, 2017), and it is challenging for the business to attain high-performance growth while competing. In a highly competitive business environment, developing new strategies that can generate new value in the face of competition or even new markets and customers is therefore essential to an organization's survival. Only then can it move on to developing other strategies (Lohtander *et al.*, 2017). Consider the market as an ocean, with rival companies acting like sharks engaged in combat and desperate attempts to emerge victorious. The company's activity system is aligned with its strategic choice of differentiation or low-cost, as indicated by the bloodshed that turns the ocean red. In the case of the company that typically delivers project-based products to the customer on demand, the blue ocean strategy is used (Aithal, 2016). According to Stambaugh, Yu, and Dubinsky (2011), the company's most valuable clients are still placing orders for the product or service at this time, and activities are planned on a project basis in close proximity to the customers.

According to Kim and Mauborgne's (2015) definition, the Blue Ocean refers to those industries that do not yet exist, have unexplored markets, have not been penetrated by rivals, and in which competition is meaningless due to the absence of established regulations governing competition. It's a company plan that venture into uncharted territory without regard to competitors (Massoudi, 2018). This tactic breaks the law of substitution between distinction and low cost by generating new value for the company and its customers (Baxter and MacLeod, 2008). Based on prior definitions, the researchers came to the conclusion that blue ocean strategy is the process of creating value in order to identify the remote portions of the market that a competitor did not address.

The Blue Ocean strategic plan creates new environments for redefining products or services where the nature of competition is not on the table and differentiation and cost leadership strategies are sought at the same time (AlQudah 2018). By offering a leap in value to the beneficiary at a reasonable cost, the "Blue Ocean Strategy" articulates a non-competitive approach that looks for fresh blue oceans free from rivalry and conflicts. This creates an incentive to keep costs low and minimize expenses in order to thwart attempts at imitation. Additionally, by generating an exchange benefit, this development benefits the community. As a result, the community, the institution, and the recipients all experience a major victory.

Benefits of Blue Ocean Strategy:

- i. **Reduced Competition:** By creating uncontested market space, companies avoid the intense competition of traditional markets.
- ii. **Increased Profitability:** Blue oceans can lead to significant revenue and profit growth by attracting a new customer base.
- iii. **Innovation:** The strategy encourages innovative thinking and can lead to breakthrough products and services.

Dimensions of Blue Ocean Strategy

Blue Ocean Strategy consists of several key components designed to help companies create new market spaces and make competition irrelevant. These components include:

Value Innovation

Value innovation is a cornerstone concept in the realm of business strategy, notably introduced as a foundational principle of Blue Ocean Strategy Kim and Renée. It represents the simultaneous pursuit of differentiation and low cost, creating a leap in value for both the company and its customers. This dual focus on innovation and value sets it apart from traditional competitive strategies that typically involve a trade-off between value creation and cost reduction. Value innovation breaks the traditional trade-off between differentiation and cost leadership. Instead of choosing one over the other, companies strive to achieve both simultaneously, creating products or services that stand out in the market while also being cost-effective (Uforo *et al.*, 2022). By offering a unique value proposition that meets new or underserved customer needs, companies can unlock new demand in the market. This approach often leads to the creation of new market spaces, or "blue oceans," where competition is minimal or nonexistent (AlQudah, 2018).

Companies can succeed by going to an uncontested market space without competition. It refers to the undiscovered market area. It is characterized by the innovation of value, creating performance and high demand. There are no limits to the experienced market, the unique nature of the market area and the innovation of value used to borrow to photograph a blue sea (Burke, Stel, Thurik, 2016), so the value of innovation for the product or service is their new strategy in net blue waters that do not disturb competition and this contributes to making unique and valuable images of consumers that prove that the Blue Ocean strategy helps them gain more satisfied customers whether they are the case or future, the value of innovation occurs in a region where the company's business has a positive impact on its cost structure and value offering to buyers (Hasan *et al.*, 2017). The innovation strategy leads to better customer performance, improved business processes, and growth. Creating a competitive advantage that includes all (business processes that primarily take into account the values provided to customers. Increasingly lasting success comes not from rival fighters, but from the creation of blue oceans from new untapped market spaces ready for growth, enabling companies to innovate or expand in order to create an ocean (Hasan *et al.*, 2017). Where no company currently operates, leaving the company growing without competition, "uncontested market space" from engaging in traditional competition, this approach represents a simultaneous pursuit of high product differentiation and low cost, making the competition irrelevant, it is successful because it attracts large numbers of customers Ebele and Eberechukwu, 2018). It often creates new consumer value while reducing costs, a market for a product where there is no competition or less competition.

Demand creation

Demand creation is a holistic approach to marketing and sales cohesion within the company (Elijah *et al.*, 2018). Through various nurture campaigns and marketing approaches, demand creation efforts aim to both create a long-term relationship between a brand and a potential buyer, and at the same time gauge and develop a prospect's purchasing interest in said brand's products/services. Building brand or product/service awareness is a vital component in the demand generation process, and often takes a continued effort and involves multiple facets of

marketing. Advanced demand creation programs typically rely on some form of proactive lead generation activities supported by more traditional market programs and processes (Dvorak, 2018).

According to Dvorak (2018), Demand creation strategies are the various approaches and techniques used by companies to stimulate interest and generate demand for their products or services. In management, demand creation refers to the process of stimulating and generating customer interest and desire for a particular product or service (Burke 2016). It involves implementing strategies and activities to increase the demand for a company's offerings in the marketplace. Effective demand creation is crucial for business growth and profitability. Here are some key points to consider from a management perspective when it comes to demand creation; market research: before creating demand, it is important to thoroughly understand the target market and customer needs.

Due to the crowded market space and increased supply of goods, the prospects for profits and growth are lower (Burke, 2016), the Blue Ocean strategy shows itself in the sale as a way to increase profitable growth for companies by creating a new demand that no competitor is competing for. Potential innovation is the most important factor that a manager should be interested in (Dvorak, 2018), developing employee mentoring and collaboration programs is the next step in implementing the Blue Ocean strategy. The latest strategy was adopted by companies to market their products and avoid negative competition. The creation of blue oceans, rather than the creation of red oceans, is done by seeking to create an indisputable market rather than competition within the current market (Burke, 2018).

Growth and Profitability

Businesses' primary goals, which determine their long-term viability, are growth and profitability. Even though they are closely related, attaining both calls for a calculated strategy that strikes a balance between the necessity of financial stability and the goal of expansion. Today's businesses face fierce competition and will stop at nothing to increase their market share. If a product is undercutting prices, there's always a chance that the business's operations could be jeopardized; in fact, the business needs to succeed without running afoul of its rivals (Burke, Stel, and Thurik, 2016).

Companies now face fierce competition, making it harder for them to make money, expand, thrive, outperform their rivals, and increase their market share which is to continue operating while implementing fresh methods and tactics to enable it to effect change (AlQudah and Hashem, 2018). A key objective for businesses, governments, and communities is to achieve higher growth through the Blue Ocean Strategy, which also creates new markets and revenues. This kind of scenario typically arises when a business seeks to expand, searching for industries or avenues to secure new business where they can enjoy a dominant market share or "blue ocean" where there is potential for increased earnings (Dvorak, 2018).

The company's goal is to outperform its competitors by being faster, cheaper, more efficient, and better at what it does. This is not connected to the strategy of operational effectiveness; rather, it is focused on making enormous profits where the product can be priced due to its unique qualities (Hong, Chai, and Ismail, 2011). By gaining a larger market share, it addresses the realities of businesses that have long been in direct competition with one another in an effort to grow profitably (Burke, Stel, Thurik, 2016). Access to blue oceans and the establishment of new markets where they may impose their rules on all entrants are two

extremely potent tools at the disposal of modern enterprises. They'll establish a flawless competitive edge for themselves that will steadily advance them toward their goals (Karaoulanis, 2018). "A consistent pattern of the strategic thinking behind the creation of new markets and industries where demand is created rather than fighting for the base of irrelevant competition," according to the researchers (Kim et al., 2007) is what they refer to as the Blue Ocean strategy (Aithal, 2016).

The Four Actions Framework:

- i. **Eliminate:** Identify which factors the industry takes for granted and should be eliminated. The organization should create new value and think carefully about excluding the factors around which organizations have competed in previous periods. Excluding some unnecessary elements, this exclusion will reduce costs and do not affect sales or quality levels. For example, the elimination of the products sale in one market location or the elimination of certain workers who slows the work process and work at high wages, as well as the elimination of some expenses which can reduce the costs of the production process. Thus, the goal of the organization is to eliminate what is considered unnecessary and has no effect on the work process (Aithal, 2016).
- ii. **Reduce:** Determine which factors should be reduced well below the industry's standard. An organization that seeks to create a blue ocean should seriously consider the activities that it overestimated in various areas, such as product design, that contributed to the increase in costs (Ekanem *et al*, 2022). Reducing some non-work-related actions, which will contribute to reducing costs. Many companies are overstating their customer service, which raises costs without profit, thus, the company reduces the volume of its investment to a certain extent such as downsizing ideas or applications that are harmful to the environment and the development of ideas that stimulate the application of environmental ideas. This can distinguish the organization from its competitors in front of its customers and stakeholders.
- iii. **Raise:** Ascertain which factors should be raised well above the industry's standard. The organization is supposed to work on increasing the concentration of some factors more than the rest of the competitors in the field of production processes, services or marketing activities, to reach a state of exclusivity and increase some things that will have the ability to increase and improve the level of quality in the products and services it provides to customers. Represent some things that will have the ability to increase and improve quality in the products required for the consumer, such as increased sales premises, demands, increase the quality level, seeking to meet customers' needs. In this way, the organization seeks to achieve competitive superiority over its competitors in the market.
- iv. **Create:** Recognize which factors should be created that the industry has never offered. The organization's implementation of the previous stages allows it to discover entirely new sources of customer value, to create new demand and to modify the strategies followed. Creating new ideas, finding ways to deliver and offer goods and services to satisfy customers or create new systems or practices that help organizations to improve its product. Innovative organizations have the ability to transform creative ideas into useful outcomes, and managers who talk about making the organization more creative usually want to stimulate innovation. The Blue Ocean

organization seeks to create new business and products, as well as create an innovative working environment and innovative production and marketing methods.

Sustainable Competitive Advantage

In today's globalized business world, organizations must constantly manage their resources to gain a competitive edge over rivals. This is because, given their privileged position, they can offer unique features for their services and/or products, giving them a competitive advantage. These challenges include potential competitors, devaluation, interest rate increases, and currency fluctuations (Guimarães, Severo, and Vasconcelos, 2017).

According to Elijah and Millicent (2018), "the organization's ability to create a defensible position on its competitors" is what can be accomplished if the company's value/cost gap is larger than that of its rivals. Gaining access to a competitive advantage is a strategic objective for the business with the highest average returns. For businesses to generate higher profits than typical, their competitive advantage needs to be sustainable. They also need to offer comparable common value and outperform their rivals in tasks that increase buyer value and necessitate a premium price (Imagha *et al.*, 2023).

According to Elijah and Millicent (2018), a firm has a competitive edge when it applies to create strategic value that is not employed concurrently by any existing or potential competitors and when other businesses are unable to replicate the advantages of this approach. According to Gaya *et al.* (2015), regulatory competitiveness is important when it comes to an organization's ability to meet national and international market standards, increase the real income of employees, and operate in free market conditions. Businesses can gain and sustain a competitive edge by recognizing and seizing opportunities, expanding into new markets, and coordinating their strategy with the utilization of their core competencies, capabilities, and core resources. Limited resources must be exceptional, unique, and unmatched in order for these benefits to last over time (Etim *et al.*, 2023).

Blue Ocean Strategy and Competitive Advantage

Kim and Mauborgne (2017) contend that the blue ocean doesn't pursue competing excellence, due to the trap of competition. This is considered to be as a good measure to be improved. Yet, in the end, the achievement of blue ocean strategy can be considered a competitive advantage. Few studies in the past were related to the implementation of the blue ocean strategy with the achievement of competing superiority such as Shared (2019) in Saudi Arabia and Bataineh and Alomyan in Jordan. According to Shared (2019) the four-dimensional influence of the blue ocean strategy referred to as The Four Action Framework on competing excellence. The author found that blue ocean strategy dimensions are positively influence the performance of Al-Rajhi Bank of Saudi Arabia. Shared also cited six paths in his research but did not test the impact of tool on competing excellence. Shared (2019) also designates that blue ocean strategy elements (Eliminate, Reduce, Raise and Create) positively correlate to competing excellence which consist of service quality, innovation, flexibility, cost, and customer response. Moreover, in Telecommunication sector in Irbid, Jordan also provides evidence of the strong influence of blue ocean strategy elements on competing excellence. From their funding, it is showed that the three-elements: create, raise, and reduce positively influence competing excellence. While the eliminate element which has no positive effect on competing excellence. Some other studies have been done by Namboodiri *et al.* (2019), Dehkordi *et al.* (2012), Hanifah *et al.* (2015), and Shared (2019). Bibliography study conducted by Namboodiri *et al.* (2019) by reviewing blue ocean strategy related articles and

analyze them using the grounded theory method. From the study, they collected 68 first-tier themes, and 9 second-level themes, which were categorized to be three main themes consisting of “innovative governance”, “integration of functional complexity”, and “catalysts” or “drivers for development”. Besides, Dehkordi et al. (2012) focuses solely on describing the differences between red ocean and blue ocean market and managers’ practical role. Hence, companies were found competing in the red ocean continuously to win the competition amid a diminished and less attractive market share, while the blue ocean is a market where competition is not relevant. The authors added that blue ocean strategy can be used as a new business model due to its ability to increase profits by creating new market. However, its implementation requires the involvement of right staff with practical ability, emphasis on leadership.

Theoretical Review

Competitive Forces Model

The Competitive Forces Model, also known as Porter’s Five Forces, remains highly relevant for understanding and achieving sustainable competitive advantage. By analyzing the structure of an industry and the intensity of competition, businesses can identify strategic opportunities and threats. Here’s how each of the Five Forces relates to the concept of sustainable competitive advantage:

Threat of New Entrants

Relevance to Sustainable Competitive Advantage:

- i. **Barriers to Entry:** High barriers to entry protect incumbent firms and contribute to sustainable competitive advantage. These barriers can include economies of scale, brand loyalty, patents, and capital requirements. For example, a company with strong brand recognition and customer loyalty, like Coca-Cola, benefits from significant barriers to entry that sustains its competitive position.
- ii. **Innovation:** Firms that continuously innovate can raise the barriers to entry, making it harder for new entrants to compete effectively. Continuous investment in research and development (R&D) and maintaining a technological edge can help sustain a competitive advantage.

2. Bargaining Power of Suppliers

Relevance to Sustainable Competitive Advantage:

- i. **Supplier Relationships:** Building strong, strategic relationships with suppliers can ensure consistent quality and favorable terms, which contribute to cost advantages and product differentiation. Companies like Apple manage supplier relationships meticulously to maintain quality and innovation while controlling costs.
- ii. **Vertical Integration:** Integrating suppliers into the company’s operations can reduce dependency on powerful suppliers and ensure a stable supply of key inputs, thus sustaining a competitive advantage.

3. Bargaining Power of Buyers

Relevance to Sustainable Competitive Advantage:

- i. **Customer Loyalty:** Creating strong brand loyalty and high switching costs can reduce buyer power. By offering unique value propositions and exceptional customer service, companies can retain customers and sustain their competitive edge. Starbucks, for example, has cultivated a strong brand and customer loyalty, making it less susceptible to buyer power.
- ii. **Differentiation:** Offering differentiated products that meet specific customer needs can reduce the bargaining power of buyers. Unique features, superior quality, or exceptional customer service can make it harder for buyers to find substitutes, sustaining a competitive advantage.

4. Threat of Substitute Products or Services

Relevance to Sustainable Competitive Advantage:

- i. **Innovation and R&D:** Continuous innovation and investment in R&D can help firms stay ahead of substitutes. By anticipating customer needs and trends, companies can develop new products or improve existing ones to stay competitive. For example, the pharmaceutical industry invests heavily in R&D to develop new drugs before patents expire and generic substitutes enter the market.
- ii. **Value Proposition:** Strengthening the overall value proposition, including product features, customer experience, and brand reputation, can mitigate the threat of substitutes. Companies like Tesla have created a strong brand and innovative products that differentiate them from traditional automotive manufacturers.

5. Rivalry among Existing Competitors

Relevance to Sustainable Competitive Advantage:

- i. **Strategic Positioning:** Effective positioning within the industry, such as focusing on niche markets or leveraging unique strengths, can help sustain a competitive advantage despite intense rivalry. For instance, luxury brands like Louis Vuitton position themselves in the high-end market, differentiating through exclusivity and quality.
- ii. **Operational Efficiency:** Improving operational efficiency to reduce costs and enhance profitability can provide a competitive edge. Companies like Toyota have sustained competitive advantages through lean manufacturing and continuous improvement practices.

Methodology

This study adopted the survey research design to explain the influence of blue ocean strategic and sustainable competitive advantage. The survey design was found suitable because of its economy; it allows the choice of demonstrative unit for the larger population through the sampling process, and collection of data from the population sample within a single frame of time. The population of this study was 157 full-time employees of Fristland Campina

Wamco, Nestle Nigeria Plc, Cadbury Nigeria Plc. and Unilever Nigeria Plc that specializes in the production and redistribution of beverages and consumables in Nigeria. A sample of 113 workers was selected using Taro Yamani formula, (1973).

$$\text{Formula } n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

N = population
 n = sample size
 e = error term

Stratified sampling technique was adopted for the study for copies of questionnaire to be proportionally allotted to different cadre of employees in the study organization. The primary data-gathering instrument developed and used by the researcher was the structured, closed-ended questionnaire. The questionnaire items were scored based on the 5-point Likert scale of 1 to 5, thus; 1 represents Strongly Disagree (SD), 2-Disagree (D), 3-Neutral (N), 4-Agree (A), and 5- Strongly Agree (SA). In the context of the conceptual model, three null hypotheses were used for this study. The hypotheses were tested using simple linear regression.

Model Specification

Model Specification; the functional model for this study is given as;

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3) \dots \dots \dots \text{equation 1}$$

Recoded to represent the variables it is presented as;

$$OP = f(SF, SP, SR)$$

$$Y = a_0 + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 \dots \dots \dots \text{equation 2.}$$

4. Data Presentation, Analysis and Findings

4.1. Summary of copies of Questionnaire Administered and Collected

Categories of Workers and Department	N0. Of copies of Questionnaire		Percentage Retrieved (%)
	Served	Retrieved	
Leadership Team	18	16	15
Sales Team	80	78	73
Medical Team	15	13	12
	113	107	95

Source: Field survey data (2024).

The result from the study was used to measure the relationship between blue ocean strategic and sustainable competitive advantage using the various constructs as shown in the research objectives.

4.2 Testing of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Hypothesis one

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of value innovation on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria.

H₁₁: There is significant influence of value innovation on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria.

Table 4.2.1 Regression analysis on value innovation and sustainable competitive advantage

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.799 ^a	.639	.637	.30171

a. Predictors: (Constant), value innovation

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	28.659	1	28.659	314.834	.000 ^b
	Residual	16.203	106	.091		
	Total	44.862	107			

a. Dependent Variable: sustainable competitive advantage

b. Predictors: (Constant), value innovation

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.466	.153		3.055	.003
	value innovation	.884	.050	.799	17.744	.000

a. Dependent Variable: sustainable competitive advantage

Source: Researcher's Computation (2024)

The model summary in table 4.2.1 shows an R- value of 0.799. This suggests a positive effect of value innovation on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria. The R square- value of 0.639 shows that 63.9% variation in value innovation was accounted for by variations in sustainable competitive advantage. The ANOVA table indicates that the regression model significantly predicts the dependents variable given the F- value of 314.834 and its corresponding P- value of 0.00. This implies that there is significant effect of value innovation on sustainable competitive advantage. Also, the B-coefficient of 0.466 implies that holding every other thing constant, the model predict 0.884 unit increase in value innovation given a unit increase in sustainable competitive advantage.

4.2.2 Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Demand creation does not significantly influence sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria.

H_{i2}: Demand creation have significantly influence sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria.

Table 4.2.2 Regression analysis on Demand creation and sustainable competitive advantage

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.825 ^a	.681	.679	.28363

a. Predictors: (Constant), Demand creation

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	30.542	1	30.542	379.666	.000 ^b
	Residual	14.319	106	.080		
	Total	44.862	107			

a. Dependent Variable: sustainable competitive advantage

b. Predictors: (Constant), Demand creation

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.210	.152		1.382	.169
	Demand creation	.962	.049	.825	19.485	.000

a. Dependent Variable: sustainable competitive advantage

Source: Researcher's Computation (2024)

The model summary in table 4.2.2 shows an R- value of 0.825. This suggests a positive effect of demand creation on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria. The R square- value of 0.681 shows that 68.1% variation in demand creation was accounted for by variations in sustainable competitive advantage. The ANOVA table indicates that the regression model significantly predicts the dependents variable given the F- value of 379.666 and its corresponding P- value of 0.00. This implies that there is significant effect of demand creation on sustainable competitive advantage. Also, the B- coefficient of 0.210 implies that holding every other thing constant, the model predict 0.962 unit increase in demand creation given a unit increase in sustainable competitive advantage.

4.2.3 Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: There is no significant influence growth and profitability on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria.

H₁₃: There is significant influence growth and profitability on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria.

Table 4.2.3 Regression analysis on growth and profitability and sustainable competitive advantage

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.725 ^a	.526	.523	.34567

a. Predictors: (Constant), growth and profitability

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23.593	1	23.593	197.456	.000 ^b
	Residual	21.269	106	.119		
	Total	44.862	107			

a. Dependent Variable: organizational sustainability

b. Predictors: (Constant) growth and profitability

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	.009	.225		.039	.969
	growth and profitability	1.015	.072	.725	14.052	.000

a. Dependent Variable: organizational sustainability

The model summary in table 4.2.3 shows an R- value of 0.725. This suggests a positive effect of growth and profitability on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria. The R square- value of 0.526 shows that 68.1% variation in growth and profitability was accounted for by variations in sustainable competitive advantage. The ANOVA table indicates that the regression model significantly predicts the dependents variable given the F- value of 197.456 and its corresponding P- value of 0.00. This implies that there is significant effect of growth and profitability on sustainable competitive advantage. Also, the B-coefficient of 0.009 implies that holding every other thing constant, the model predict 1.015 unit increase in growth and profitability given a unit increase in sustainable competitive advantage.

Discussion of Findings

The study was carried out to examine the effect of blue ocean strategy on sustainable competitive advantage in FMCG industries in Nigeria. The result of the study showed that there is a significant influence of blue ocean strategy variables on sustainable competitive advantage in FMCG industries in Nigeria. Looking at the result of the simple linear regression analysis to determine the influence of value innovation, demand creation and growth and profitability on sustainable competitive advantage in fast moving consumer good industry in Nigeria. The R square- value of 0.637 shows that 63.7% variation in value innovation was accounted for by variations in sustainable competitive advantage. This implies that there is significant effect of value creation on sustainable competitive advantage.

This is in line with other studies in the literature. This give assurance that firms who must gain competitive advantage has to be sensitive enough to its business environment to identify market opportunities and threats before competitors do, allowing them to act swiftly and decisively. In the linear model demand creation showed a statistically significant influence on sustainable competitive advantage with its ability to explain 67 per cent of the change in sustainable competitive advantage. And finally the result from this study showed that growth and profitability is statistically significant influence on sustainable competitive advantage with its ability to explain 52.3 per cent of the change in sustainable competitive advantage.

5. Conclusion

By substituting competitive advantage for value innovation, demand creation, growth and profitability as the main objectives where businesses must generate customer demand and penetrate undiscovered markets blue ocean strategy aims to completely flip the conventional wisdom on strategic management. The focus of empirical research to until has been on case studies of profitable businesses, which has limited the study's capacity to be broadly applicable. This is a serious flaw because the argument oscillates between cynicism (competitive strategy) and faith (blue ocean), with the latter stating that there are enough unexplored market opportunities for most businesses to use blue ocean as a general managerial strategy, rendering competition irrelevant. On the other hand, competitive strategy suggests that there are only a few short-term possibilities for businesses to discover unexplored markets, which will eventually be diminished by imitation and competition. In these situations, managers should concentrate on competitive strategy. A theoretical model that shows how competitive and blue ocean strategies can coexist as short- and long-term strategic priority is described in order to examine the prevalence of either strategic school of thinking in practice. An empirical model that employs a vast data set on the fast-moving consumer goods sectors to test hypotheses brings statistical evidence to light on this argument.

6 Recommendations

- i. It was recommended that value innovation is a cornerstone of the blue ocean strategy and represents the simultaneous pursuit of differentiation and low cost, creating a leap in value for both the company and its customers.
- ii. That the fast-moving consumer goods industries should be focusing on creating demand rather than competing for existing demand, companies can achieve sustainable growth, build strong brands, and maintain a competitive edge in an ever-evolving market landscape.
- iii. That the fast-moving consumer goods industries should see growth and profitability as fundamental to a company's success, providing the financial resources, strategic flexibility, and competitive advantages needed to thrive in a dynamic market environment. These factors contribute to a company's ability to innovate, attract investment, and sustain long-term operations, ultimately ensuring its place in the market and its contribution to the broader economy.

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